

The History of Quantum Computing

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18th November 2021

1 Abstract

This article addresses the history of quantum computing. In this context, the origins of this emerging scientific field, its initial purposes, and future prospects are discussed. Furthermore, the technologies derived from quantum computing and their potential to transform and enhance human life in various technological domains are also examined.

Keywords: Quantum Computing; History; Applications; Present; Future; Technology; Science.

2 Introduction

This paper addresses important topics related to the field of quantum computing. This area has recently shown significant advances and holds the potential to revolutionize the future of computing. Therefore, understanding it becomes increasingly relevant. The purpose of this document is to clarify the basic concepts of the field, highlight key moments in its history, and present the expectations regarding its future and possible applications.

3 Basic Concepts of Quantum Computing

To understand quantum computing, it is necessary to grasp certain key concepts that have led to significant advancements in quantum theory. Some comparisons will also be made with classical and modern computing to illustrate these concepts more clearly.

In traditional computers, the smallest and most essential component is the transistor, whose function is to allow or block the flow of electrons. This enables it to represent two

distinct values (when electrons pass through and when they do not), namely, 1 or 0. In classical computing, this output is known as a "bit".

In quantum computing, the smallest unit of information is called a "qubit", which can be, for instance, a photon. The values 0 and 1 may correspond to the vertical or horizontal polarization of this photon. However, unlike classical bits, a qubit is not limited to just these two states. Based on quantum theory, a qubit can exist in any proportion between the two states—a phenomenon known as superposition. As long as the qubit's value is not measured, it remains in superposition and, consequently, its value is undetermined—or more precisely, it embodies all possible values simultaneously. Once the value is measured, however, the qubit is forced into a definite state (in the case of the photon, either vertically or horizontally polarized), corresponding to 0 or 1. Because qubits can exist in all possible combinations simultaneously, the number of possible states in a system increases exponentially with the number of qubits, specifically by powers of two [1].

Another fundamental concept that, along with superposition, underpins the advancement and significance of quantum computing is entanglement [2]. This concept describes a very strong correlation between multiple qubits, such that a change in the state of one qubit instantaneously affects its entangled partners. Thus, by measuring—and thereby collapsing the state—of one qubit, it becomes possible to infer the state of its entangled counterparts without directly measuring them.

The next step toward more complex systems involves the use of quantum gates (analogous to logic gates in classical computing) and the manipulation of qubits and their probabilities. In classical computing, logic gates receive a set of inputs and produce a determined output. A quantum gate, on the other hand, receives a superposition of states, manipulates the associated probabilities, and produces another superposition as output.

Therefore, a quantum computer takes a set of qubits, applies quantum gates, entangles them, and manipulates their possible states. Finally, it measures them, collapsing their superpositions into an actual sequence of ones and zeros. This enables the simultaneous processing of all possible outcomes of an operation. By exploiting superposition and entanglement, quantum computing makes it possible to reach and verify results—through multiple iterations—much faster than a classical computer could.

4 Brief History of Quantum Computing up to the 2000s

The idea of a computational device based on quantum mechanics was already being explored in the 1970s by physicists and computer scientists. It emerged when researchers were investigating the fundamental physical limits of computation. If technology continued to follow Moore's Law ¹ then the ever-decreasing size of circuits embedded in

¹The observation made in 1965 by Gordon Moore, co-founder of Intel, stated that the number of transistors per square inch on integrated circuits had doubled approximately every 18 months since the invention of the integrated circuit.

silicon chips would eventually reach a point where the individual elements would be no larger than a few atoms [3]. However, since the physical laws that govern the behavior and properties of circuits at the atomic scale are inherently quantum—not classical—by nature, the natural question arose as to whether a new type of computer could be created based on the principles of quantum physics.

One of the early influences in the 1970s was the physicist Stephen Wiesner, from Columbia University, who suggested that quantum properties of photons could be used to generate “quantum money” that would be impossible to counterfeit. According to his vision, this would involve storing a few dozen photons in light traps within each banknote and ensuring that their polarization states were known only by the issuing bank. Since quantum states cannot be copied, the banknote could never be duplicated, and anyone wishing to verify its authenticity would only need to present it to the issuing bank, which could then use its prior knowledge of the polarizations to validate it. In this way, Wiesner proposed that quantum information processing could be a more effective method for executing cryptographic tasks — an idea that inspired a generation of quantum physicists to develop quantum cryptography, aimed at transmitting messages with enhanced security [4].

However, Wiesner only published his work, "Conjugate Coding" [5] in 1983 in the ACM SIGACT News, while the first four articles on quantum information had already been published by Alexander Holevo (1973), Roman Pavlovich Poplavskii (1975), and Roman Ingarden (1976). Starting with Holevo, a Russian mathematician who made substantial contributions to the mathematical foundations of quantum theory, quantum statistics, and quantum information theory—in 1973, he published his paper "Bounds for the Quantity of Information Transmitted by a Quantum Communication Channel" [6], in which he derived an upper bound for the amount of classical information that can be extracted from a set of quantum states (known as accessible information) through quantum measurements. This result became known as the Holevo Theorem [7].

Poplavskii, in his work “Thermodynamical Models of Information Processing” [8], demonstrated the computational infeasibility of simulating quantum systems on classical computers due to the principle of superposition. Meanwhile, the Polish physicist and mathematician Roman Ingarden published an article in 1976 titled “Quantum Information Theory” [9], which outlined one of the earliest attempts to create a theory of quantum information. He showed that Shannon’s classical information theory could not be directly generalized to the quantum case ². Instead, it was possible to construct a quantum information theory that is a generalization of Shannon’s theory — through a generalized quantum mechanics of open systems and a generalized concept of observables, called semi-observable.

²Shannon’s theory focused on the possibilities of optimizing message transmission, treating messages as sequences of symbols and disregarding their meaning. Furthermore, it defined the components of the communication model, such as the sender, receiver, and channel.

However, the most widely recognized contributions were made only in the early 1980s by Paul A. Benioff from the Argonne National Laboratory in Illinois, David Deutsch from the University of Oxford, Richard Feynman from the California Institute of Technology, and Kazuhiro Igeta and Yoshihisa Yamamoto from the Tokyo Institute of Technology.

Initially, Paul Benioff is regarded as one of the founding figures of quantum computing, having been the first to describe a mechanical model of a quantum computer in 1980. In his work entitled “The Computer as a Physical System: A Microscopic Quantum Mechanical Hamiltonian Model of Computers as Represented by Turing Machines” [10], it was demonstrated that a computer could operate according to the laws of quantum mechanics, presenting a description of the Schrödinger equation applied to Turing machines. In May 1981, at the first conference on the Physics of Computation held at MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) [11], Paul Benioff and Richard Feynman gave talks on quantum computing. Upon attending Feynman’s lecture, Benioff observed that it seemed impossible to efficiently simulate the evolution of a quantum system on a classical computer. Two years after this conference, Benioff developed his original model of a Turing machine based on quantum mechanics, a milestone that is often referred to as the “big bang” of quantum computing.

Building on this foundation in the field, in 1985, David Deutsch published the article “Quantum theory, the Church-Turing principle and the universal quantum computer” [12], in which it is stated that a universal quantum computer, like a universal Turing machine, is capable of simulating any other Turing machine, but with improved efficiency and notable properties that cannot be reproduced by any classical Turing machine. This gave rise to what became known as the Church-Turing-Deutsch principle. The universal quantum computer would be able to simulate any other quantum computer with, at most, a polynomial slowdown. Finally, it was only in 1988 that Yoshihisa Yamamoto and Kazuhiro Igeta published the article “Quantum mechanical computers with single atom and photon fields” [13], in which they proposed the first physical realization of a quantum computer, including Feynman’s CNOT gate. Their approach used atoms and photons, laying the groundwork for modern quantum computing and network protocols that employ photons to transmit qubits and atoms to perform two-qubit operations.

With regard to progress in quantum algorithms, it is noted that this began in the 1990s with the discovery of the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm in 1992, as presented in the article “Rapid solutions of problems by quantum computation” [14] by David Deutsch and Richard Jozsa. The Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm was proposed for a class of problems that could be solved more efficiently by their quantum algorithm, whereas any classical deterministic algorithm would face considerable difficulty, being prone to faults and errors. This was perhaps the first result in the area of computational complexity for quantum computers, demonstrating that they were capable of performing certain well-defined computational tasks with better performance than any classical computer.

In 1993, Daniel Simon from the University of Montreal introduced Simon’s algorithm, described in “On the Power of Quantum Computation” [15]. This contribution originated

from Simon's invention of an oracle problem for which a quantum computer would be exponentially faster than the best classical algorithm on a conventional machine [16]. As a result, this provided compelling evidence that the quantum model might possess significantly greater theoretical complexity power than the probabilistic Turing machine.

Simon's algorithm laid the foundation for Shor's algorithm, discovered by Peter Shor from AT&T Bell Labs in New Jersey in 1994, and reported in his work "Polynomial-Time Algorithms for Prime Factorization and Discrete Logarithms on a Quantum Computer" [17]. This algorithm enables a quantum computer to efficiently factor large integers, thus solving both the factorization problem and the discrete logarithm problem. As a result, it can theoretically break many cryptosystems currently in use. This invention generated widespread interest in quantum computers, extending even beyond the physics community.

In the same year, 1994, Cirac and Zoller proposed the experimental implementation of the quantum CNOT gate using trapped ions, which led to the research entitled "Quantum Computations with Cold Trapped Ions" [18]. One year later, in 1995, Peter Shor and Andrew Steane independently proposed the first quantum error correction schemes. Shor published the article "Good Quantum Error-Correcting Codes Exist" [19], while Steane published "Multiple-Particle Interference and Quantum Error Correction" [20].

In 1996, following the proposal of Cirac and Zoller, Christopher Monroe and David Wineland at NIST (Boulder, Colorado) successfully implemented the first quantum logic gate (the controlled-NOT or CNOT gate) using trapped ions. Also in 1996, Lov Grover from Bell Labs invented a quantum search algorithm, described in "A fast quantum mechanical algorithm for database search" [21], which leveraged the phenomenon of quantum parallelism to solve search problems. This algorithm offered a quadratic speedup compared to classical algorithms. Although this improvement was not as dramatic as that offered by algorithms for factoring, discrete logarithms, or physical simulations, the algorithm could be applied to a much broader range of problems [22].

Finally, just a year later, at the end of the 1990s, the first model for quantum computation based on nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) techniques was proposed. This technique was experimentally realized in 1998 with a 2-qubit register and later extended to 7 qubits at the National Laboratory of Los Alamos in 2000. Moreover, on July 31, 2000, Arun K. Pati and Samuel L. Braunstein proved the no-deleting theorem, establishing that it is impossible to delete a copy of a quantum state [23].

5 Quantum Computing in the 21st Century

In the first year of the 21st century, scientists Emanuel Knill, Raymond Laflamme, and Gerard Milburn, from the Department of Energy at the National Laboratory of Los Alamos and the Centre for Quantum Computing Technology at the University of Queensland, made significant progress in the pursuit of a functional quantum computer by ex-

ploring existing technologies in a novel and unexpected way. It was demonstrated by the scientists that optical quantum computing is feasible using only single-photon sources, beam splitters, phase shifters, and photon detectors. This opened new avenues for further computational experiments in this field, as the analysis of photon disturbances is appealing due to the simplicity with which it can be observed [24].

Still in that same year, shifting from optics to the electromagnetic field, Michael N. Leuenberger and Daniel Loss published the article “Quantum computing in molecular magnets” [25], in which they proposed an implementation of Grover’s algorithm using molecular magnets. These magnets are solid-state systems with large spin, such that their intrinsic spin states make them natural candidates for single-particle systems. In this way, it was shown that, theoretically, molecular magnets can be used to construct dense and efficient memory devices based on Grover’s algorithm.

In 2004, a research group led by Rainer Blatt, an Austrian-German experimental physicist, in collaboration with a team from the National Institute of Standards and Technology in Boulder, Colorado (USA), managed for the first time to transfer quantum information from one atom to another in a fully controlled manner (teleportation) [26]. The scientific journal *Nature* reported on these experiments, which were conducted independently, and featured them prominently on the cover. In this experiment, described in the article “Deterministic quantum teleportation of atomic qubits” [27], three particles were positioned in a segmented ion trap that facilitates the addressing of individual qubits. By the end of the experiment, an average fidelity of 78% was achieved, surpassing the fidelity of other protocols that did not employ this entanglement technique. Furthermore, two years later, Blatt’s team successfully entangled up to eight atoms in a controlled manner, thereby creating the first quantum computer with 8 qubits, which was presented at the University of Innsbruck [28].

In 2007, physicists from the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) transferred information between two “artificial atoms” through electronic vibrations in a microfabricated aluminum cable, demonstrating a new component for potential ultra-powerful quantum computers of the future [29]. The setup resembles a miniature version of a cable television transmission line, but with some powerful additional features, including superconducting circuits with zero electrical resistance and multitasking data bits that obey the unusual rules of quantum physics.

A year later, in 2008, a team of scientists from Princeton University in New Jersey, the University of Oxford in the United Kingdom, and the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory of the Energy Department of California, partially supported by the National Science Foundation, reported in the journal *Nature* that they had succeeded in storing information in the nucleus of an atom [30]. In the experiment they conducted, the system utilized the nucleus and electrons of a phosphorus atom embedded in a silicon crystal. Both the electron and the nucleus behaved as tiny quantum magnets capable of storing quantum information. The researchers then transferred the information to the nucleus, where it persisted for a significantly longer duration—around 3 to 4 seconds. This was

a major discovery, as prior to this technique, the longest duration quantum information could be preserved in silicon was less than one-tenth of a second.

In 2009, a team from NIST led by Jonathan Home revealed the first small-scale device that utilized ultracold ions to separately demonstrate all the necessary steps for quantum computation. These included initializing the qubits, storing them in ions, performing a logical operation on one or two qubits, transferring information between different locations in the processor, and reading the individual qubit results[31]. Home’s setup achieved an overall accuracy of 94% — an impressive figure for a quantum device, though not yet sufficient for a large-scale quantum computer.

Subsequently, in 2010, physicists from Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz, led by Dr. Arno Rauschenbeutel, developed a quantum interface that connects particles of light to atoms [32]. The interface is based on an ultrathin glass fiber and is suitable for the transmission of quantum information, which is an essential prerequisite for quantum communication. According to Rauschenbeutel, this interface could be used for secure data transmission through quantum cryptography, as well as for quantum computers.

However, it was only in 2017 that two major advances were made in the field, led by IBM, with the development of a universal quantum computer with 17 qubits—meaning it had the capacity to solve a variety of quantum problems, unlike other more specialized models [33]. Furthermore, at the end of that same year, the company announced the development of the first 50-qubit computer [34] [35] [36]marking a significant milestone, as this was the largest number of quantum bits estimated to be simulatable by the best classical supercomputers. This achievement paved the way for future advances in the quantum field. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that this computer did not yet prove the concept.

In January 2019, IBM continued to demonstrate its dominance in the field when it unveiled the “Q System One,” the first quantum computer that could be accessed via the cloud and came equipped with advanced refrigeration systems [37]. In the same year, researchers from Google declared the much-anticipated “quantum supremacy” when the company’s 53-qubit chip, named “Sycamore,” took approximately 200 seconds to perform an operation that would take the best classical computers more than 10,000 years to complete [38].

Although not yet as developed as classical computing technology—partly due to being relatively recent—quantum computing is steadily approaching broader public accessibility. In 2021, the private company IBM, in collaboration with Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, put the first commercial quantum computer into operation [39]. Until then, the public only had access to quantum computing through cloud-based processing. In this regard, the German government allocated 2 billion euros [40] to ensure the scaling of qubits in each supercomputer, in an effort to anticipate the fact that the development of classical supercomputers is gradually approaching its physical limits.

Another important step taken that year came from the Canadian company D-Wave, which has been working on the integration of classical and quantum computers. The

company utilized a system called a quantum annealer, a more limited version of a quantum computer [39].

Also in 2021, on November 16, IBM unveiled the most powerful quantum computer in the world [41]. This computer, called Eagle, operates with 127 qubits and, according to the company, has twice the power of Zuchongzhi, the 56-qubit Chinese quantum computer revealed in July of that year. Zuchongzhi had previously been considered the most powerful machine in its category, capable of solving in 70 minutes a task that classical supercomputers would take at least 8 years to compute. Zaira Nazario, Technical Manager of Quantum Computing Theory and Applications at IBM, stated to El País that Eagle represents a milestone by surpassing the 100-qubit threshold. She believes it has already reached a point at which its computational power can no longer be simulated by classical computers, since, according to IBM, the number of classical bits required to match the computational capacity of this new processor exceeds the number of atoms in the more than 7.5 billion people currently alive [42].

6 The Future of Quantum Computing

"From optimizing aircraft routes to refining robotic trajectories, problems that until now have seemed impossible for current technologies will become feasible through the use of quantum computing and its dissemination over time. In all industries, quantum computing will address a wide range of problems, from optimization to simulation and machine learning," according to the multinational company Honeywell [43].

Thus, it can be understood that quantum computing has a prosperous future ahead, filled with potential innovations, both for large corporations and in everyday life. This emerging science is expected to influence various fields of technology, such as aerospace, chemistry, healthcare, robotics, and finance.

In the aerospace sector, quantum computing could significantly assist in determining optimal flight routes, taking into account numerous environmental variables, temperature conditions, and weather patterns—helping to avoid storms or unfavorable weather and reducing turbulence. Moreover, this new technology would enable the preselection of the best airports for distributing aircraft spare parts, as well as for allocating and managing resources for crew members, passengers, and more, while minimally affecting maintenance schedules.

In the field of chemistry, multiple applications of this emerging science are expected, such as the ability to simulate the properties and behaviors of new molecular structures. With this technology, it will become possible to predict and model new substances and molecules, helping to avoid potential issues that might arise from these components, and exponentially expanding the creative scope for the development of innovative chemical compounds—thus driving greater innovation in this domain.

In the healthcare and pharmaceutical sectors, quantum computing is expected to sig-

nificantly accelerate the process from discovering a new treatment to its delivery to patients. This would make advancements in healthcare faster, safer, and more responsive to current real-world needs, including the ability to combat challenges such as new pandemics more rapidly and effectively. Furthermore, this new science could reduce the costs associated with discovering and manufacturing new medical treatments, making them more affordable and accessible to the population.

In the areas of logistics and robotics, quantum technology will be crucial for improving the localization, assembly, and positioning of sensors—key components responsible for collecting data and integrating it into robots. This enables machine learning and allows robots to make more significant and accurate decisions. Consequently, quantum computing will enhance, accelerate, and increase the precision and efficiency of these processes, including determining optimal movement paths for robots in factories and warehouses.

Finally, in the financial sector, the combination of quantum mechanics and computing could lead to the identification of the most profitable investment opportunities by analyzing numerous variables that influence stock price fluctuations and generated profits. Additionally, it will become possible to detect potential fraud and anonymous transactions more quickly, further enhancing the security of financial transactions and bank accounts.

In summary, it can be stated that there are numerous areas of technology in which quantum computing could be—or will be—highly active and beneficial for their advancement, as well as for increasing efficiency and improving digital security. However, to achieve these technological advancements, it is estimated that it will take at least 5 to 10 years for the simplest developments to become viable for both society and large corporations.

Furthermore, several challenges must be overcome by computer engineering for this technology to become truly viable and widely adopted. Among these challenges is the loss of information and memory in superconducting qubits, as under these conditions, qubits frequently lose information within a few nanoseconds. Another significant issue is the high error rate generated by quantum computers, as it is extremely difficult to build one with low error margins. In addition, environmental instability and the lack of suitable materials contribute to the loss of quantum data, reducing the operational lifespan of a qubit.

Moreover, it is necessary to perform logical operations while working with qubits in order to reduce potential electromagnetic noise interference, which can decrease a qubit's coherence. Therefore, correcting errors in quantum computing, when compared to classical computing, is particularly challenging, as such errors are continuous, difficult to identify, and may result in the loss of data stored in qubits.

Thus, although there are multiple promising fields of application and a highly prosperous future for quantum computing, enabling these innovations and emerging technologies to become reality will require overcoming numerous scientific and technical challenges. This creates a growing need to further understand the behavior of qubits and the problems associated with them, as well as how to mitigate these issues.

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